

Research Article

Tycoon Game Board

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Abstract: As more markets expand their business internationally, it is encouraged for the younger generation to learn knowledge about trade. Hence, we invented the Tycoon Game Board which is a board educational game with educational purposes to emphasize trade knowledge that focuses on export and tax. Tycoon Game Board can be played by 4 - 6 players who are also known as exporters in this game. Each player will gain a sum of money as their capital. Starting by rolling the dice, the exporters will begin to make a decision whether or not to enter the market. An amount of fee should be paid to secure the entry market with its export goods. If other exporters happen to stop at others' own space, they will be charged a tax. There are four corners in the board game which are occupied with bonus (begin), tax sanction, port trade and penalty. The exporter who accumulates the highest trading revenue will be declared the winner of the Tycoon Game Board. The educational and entrepreneurial potential of Tycoon Game Board can be effectively utilized by students, lecturers, and traders or startup companies for both learning and business development purposes. Tycoon Game Board offers valuable benefits to communities such as educational institutions and individuals seeking to enhance their trade strategy.

Keywords: educational game; board game; trading knowledge.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Many organizations or firms are now focusing on globalizing their business since in the digitalization era it gives better exposure for marketing products. However, it is difficult for a first timer or a start-up company to get a better view on the process of exporting and tax imposed from countries to certain goods. So, Tycoon Game Board is an educational game board that emphasizes export and tax duty imposed. This game's purpose is to give a basic simulation for a firm to penetrate other countries' markets and the tax imposed for their exported goods. It provides an interactive and engaging way to apply theoretical knowledge to real-world scenarios.

Layout of the game consists of a square board with the size of 30 inch by 30 inch divided into 24 spaces including countries, quests and special places such as "Go", "Penalty", "Port Trade", and

“Trade Sanction”. There are also game pieces for a player or will be called as exporter during the game. The games include paper currency for transaction purposes while paying the tax or entering the market. Tycoon Game Board provides a country card where it contains details of tax imposed.

The gameplay overview of Tycoon Game Board is that exporters move around the board based on the number of dice. Each place that exporters stop, they need to determine whether to pay the money to enter the market or not. The strategy is purely based on exporter analysis on which market has a higher revenue or less tax imposed. Exporters can gain revenue from the tax imposed on other exporters that landed in each of their own countries. The objective is to dominate the board by acquiring countries' markets.

In conclusion, our project, Tycoon Game Board, is to give exposure on trade and tax processes. Spread of knowledge among institutional or start-up companies can ease their difficulty in getting a better view of basic information in securing globalization. It is inspired by the game board Monopoly and Saidina which are known among all ages. However, Tycoon Game Board have different approaches in the purpose where the game focuses on global tax impose. Besides, the familiarity in rules, Tycoon Game Board gives exposure on new knowledge where no other game board has used.

1.1 Problem Statement

In an increasingly globalized market, understanding trade fundamentals especially taxation and tariffs is vital, yet many individuals lack this essential knowledge. The Tycoon Game Board addresses this gap by offering an engaging, educational experience that equips players with critical trade skills, simulating real-world scenarios such as market entry, tax obligations, and strategic decision-making.

Designed for 4-6 players, each representing exporters, the game begins with an initial capital investment. Players roll dice to navigate the board, making decisions about entering markets by paying market entry fees for their export goods. Players may land on opponents' spaces, incurring tax penalties, thereby emphasizing the importance of strategic positioning. The board features four corners with specific functions: Begin (bonus), Tax Sanction, Port Trade, and Penalty, creating diverse gameplay dynamics. The objective is to accumulate the highest trading revenue, encouraging players to develop and implement effective trade strategies.

Targeting students, educators, traders, and startups, the Tycoon Game Board serves as a valuable learning tool within educational institutions and for individuals seeking to enhance their business acumen. It not only promotes financial literacy but also fosters a deeper understanding of export dynamics and taxation. Engaging in this interactive format helps players gain confidence in navigating international trade challenges, ultimately preparing them for real-world business scenarios (British Council, 2023).

This game stands out as an effective resource for those wishing to improve their trade strategy knowledge, making learning enjoyable and relevant. With the potential to bridge the knowledge gap in trade and taxation, the Tycoon Game Board is an essential addition to educational and entrepreneurial settings.

1.1 Objectives

The Tycoon Game Board is an educational instrument designed to teach players, particularly younger generations, about the principles of international trade. As exporters, players make realistic market entry decisions, paying fees to gain access to markets and dealing with the financial consequences of taxes and tariffs when landing on other players' areas. This hands-on simulation helps

players learn difficult trading principles, which sparks a greater interest in business and economics. With the goal of accumulating the most trading revenue, participants are urged to strategy and manage their capital wisely, demonstrating the value of financial planning and long-term thinking in international trade.

Beyond individual games, Tycoon Game Board has enormous community and educational value. It serves as a learning tool for students, educators, and start-up businesses, giving them hands-on experience in trade strategy and finance. The game can be used in the classroom to educate business principles, as well as a development tool for individuals in the early stages of business planning to make trade knowledge more accessible. Tycoon Game Board's engaging method allows communities to increase trade knowledge and entrepreneurial abilities, helping to cultivate a generation better prepared to succeed in the global economy.

2. NOVELTY

By enabling players to experience real-world trading situations that conventional approaches would miss, the "Tycoon Game Board" turns abstract trade ideas into a useful and entertaining educational tool. Players get important insights into global trade by making strategic choices about things like managing tariffs or taxes, export logistics, and market access. While tariffs are levied on imports to safeguard home industries or raise money (Nevil, 2024), market access refers to a company's or country's capacity to sell products and services internationally, sometimes with an emphasis on international commerce (Kenton, 2024). Order processing, shipping, inventory management, and handling of export goods are all included in export logistics (Ghangurde, n.d.). By mimicking the characteristics of international markets, such as taxing rivals and paying market entrance fees. Tycoon's pushes players to evaluate risks, choose investments, and fight for market supremacy while encouraging strategic thinking and useful trading abilities.

The 'Tycoon Game Board' is a unique tool for making complicated trade dynamics entertaining and approachable. Prices and the actions of producers and consumers are influenced by market dynamics. When supply and demand for a particular good or service fluctuate, these factors provide price signals in a market (Banton, 2024). Any sector or government policy may be impacted by market dynamics (Banton, 2024). It is perfect for teaching business concepts like trade barriers, tariffs, tax techniques, and bulk commerce since its elements such as trade port zones, tax penalties, and market entrance fees reflect real-world economic principles. Any law or policy that limits international commerce, particularly taxes, quotas and licenses is referred to as a trade barrier (Vipond, 2024). It is appropriate for a variety of audiences due to its educational versatility in which entrepreneurs can practice market entry tactics and navigate international competition, educators can use it as an interactive tool for courses in international business or economics, and students can acquire fundamental trade knowledge through engaging play.

Essentially, Tycoon Game Board distinguishes itself by fusing education and fun, providing a useful instrument for fostering strategic decision-making, financial literacy, and practical business acumen. It is a unique and adaptable tool for academic institutions and business experts alike since it can replicate the intricacies of global commerce in an approachable manner. Players may improve their entrepreneurial and strategic thinking abilities as well as their grasp of commerce by playing this game and gaining useful information. The capacity to assess the current situation and resolve intricate issues in order to make plans for future success is known as strategic thinking (Osman, 2024).

3. COMMERCIALIZATION POTENTIAL

In today's market, where education and entertainment often mix, the business possibility for Tycoon Game Board is a game that focuses on taxes and tariffs which are important. People are looking for fun ways to learn about complicated economic ideas, and these games can fill a need. These games can appeal to a wide range of people, such as educators, strategy fans, and players who care about social issues, by focusing on both niche markets and cultural importance.

The possibility for making money in niche markets is especially high. Fans of strategy games will enjoy Tycoon Game Board, which is a challenging and interesting game that makes you think about how economies work. This group likes games that require a lot of strategy and deep gameplay, which makes this kind of game attractive. This game could also be used in training sessions by groups that teach about economics and public policy, which could lead to bulk buying for workshops and educational programs. Working with NGOs or think tanks can help the game get more attention because these groups may use it for outreach or lobbying, which can reach even more people.

When it comes to culture, the ongoing news stories about taxes and trade policies offer big chances to make money. People who are interested in current events may want to play a board game with these themes. The game can then be used to start a talk or teach about complicated issues. By using current events and situations from real life, the game can stay current and encourage deep conversations among players. Working together with teachers or policymakers to make tools like lesson plans or discussion guides can also make it more appealing. This means that the game can be used for more than just fun. It can also be used to teach and encourage social interaction, which increases its business potential even more.

4. BENEFITS TO COMMUNITY

Tycoon Game Board provides benefits to the community especially to educational institutions and students. Game-based learning can increase student motivation to improve their trade knowledge by making learning more interesting. This is because motivation is a key factor in student achievement. Hence, when students engage in game boards, they are more likely to participate actively, gain information, and develop a passion for learning. At times, traditional methods can be boring, but games give an element of fun and competition. For instance, teachers or lecturers may include the Tycoon Game Board into their lectures to provide students with interactive experiences by demonstrating the ideas in action. Moreover, in this game, students actively buy land, manage money, and make financial decisions, creating an immersive learning experience. Thus, institutions that integrate trading board games into the educational experience, not only make learning more enjoyable but also equip students with practical skills that can be applied in the real-world situations, preparing them for future challenges in their personal and professional life.

5. FEEDBACK FROM COMMUNITY

Figure 1. The results of the questionnaire conducted among students and the general public.

Based on the results above, 85% of respondents showed the highest level of interest in trade and tax knowledge. This suggests that most people are keen to learn more about trade, likely because it involves various aspects such as import and export activities. On the other hand, only 15% of students and the general public expressed the least interest in trade and tax knowledge. This may be because some of them are already familiar with these topics through online news, television, and social media. As a result, they might feel less inclined to seek further information on trade and tax matters.

Figure 2. The results of the questionnaire conducted among students and the general public.

Based on Figure 2, all students and members of the general public responded 'yes' to the idea of playing a board game where they can build a business empire and trade goods with other players. This strong positive response indicates that they believe such a game would be both enjoyable and beneficial. Many feel that a board game centered on business and trade could provide a realistic and engaging way to simulate the challenges of running a business, making strategic decisions, and negotiating with others. It suggests that participants recognize the potential for this type of game to enhance skills like critical thinking, teamwork, and business management while offering an entertaining experience.

Figure 3. The results of the questionnaire conducted among students and the general public.

Based on the results, 40% of people engage with board games that simulate business and trade scenarios 'rarely,' while 10% engage 'frequently,' 20% 'never,' and 30% 'occasionally.' This trend may be due to the fact that most people are more familiar with board games like Monopoly and Saidina, which focus on buying property and managing money. Additionally, games specifically designed to simulate business and trade are less common in the market, and many people are not aware of them, leading to less frequent engagement with this type of game.

Figure 4. The results of the questionnaire conducted among students and the general public.

Based on the figure, the main motivation for 40% of respondents to play a trade-themed game like the 'Tycoon Game Board' is the fun and competitive gameplay. They also see it as a way to spend quality time with family and friends, while relieving stress from work. On the other hand, only 5% are motivated by the game's unique mechanics and strategies, likely because trade and tax-themed games are new to them. As they play, they can explore strategies for minimizing taxes and trading between countries, which adds an educational aspect to the game.

6. PRODUCT DETAILS

Figure 5. The Board of The Tycoon Game Board

Figure 6. The Question Card of The Tycoon Game Board

Figure 7. The Money of The Tycoon Game Board

Figure 8. The Country Card of The Tycoon Game Board

7. CONCLUSION AND REFLECTION

In conclusion, Tycoon Game Board offers an innovative approach to teaching trade concepts through a game board. The Tycoon Game Board is more than just a game, it is a fun and engaging way to learn about the world of international trade. By putting the players in the role of importer or exporter, it allows the player to experience the challenges and strategies involved in navigating markets like dealing with taxes, and making smart business decisions. The game's design, which includes various scenarios and challenges. It can also help to enhance their understanding of trade dynamics in a practical context.

Moreover, the Tycoon Game Board encourages collaboration and healthy competition among players. The positive feedback from the players indicates a strong interest in trade and tax knowledge, suggesting that this game successfully addresses a gap in traditional educational methods that often fail to engage students in these critical subjects. As they navigate the game, they gain insights that are directly applicable to real-life situations, preparing them for future careers in business. This game board is also a valuable educational tool that makes learning about international trade engaging and relevant.

Reflecting on its impact, the Tycoon Game Board is a stepping stone for the next generation of business leaders, helping them to become informed, capable and confident in their understanding of trade and economics. In summary, Tycoon Game Board not only provides a fun game and competitive environment for players but also equips them with essential knowledge that can be applied in real-world business contexts, making it a valuable resource for students, educators and aspiring entrepreneurs alike.

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